

Proposed Content Marketing Strategy Improvement of Leap-Telkom Digital to Increase Brand Awareness

Vietra Shauma Ranabilla

School of Business and Management, Institut Teknologi Bandung

ABSTRACT: With the movement of IndiHome as the previous main product of Telkom Indonesia to Telkomsel, Telkom Indonesia is currently struggling with enhancing their digital products performance. Telkom implements its transformation from telecommunication to digital telecommunication state-owned enterprise. With that, Telkom wants to focus on enhancing its digital products. However, in its implementation, Leap faces the effort of increasing its brand awareness. Based on the author's findings from initial survey, the potential target customers are still not familiar with Leap nor Telkom's digital products. Moreover, this problem is also supported by the previous performance of Leap's website from its total users and engagement. The spread of Telkom's digital products knowledge to internal Telkom employees is also not distributed equally. With this, the author conducts research to improve Leap-Telkom Digital in hopes of improving its brand awareness. The research is using Gap analysis, Brand Building Blocks, Customer-Based Brand Equity (CBBE) pyramid, and internal interview to find the deeper problem of what's causing low brand awareness of Leap. And then, using theory of Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC), as well as weighting and rating method, the author proposed a Content Marketing strategy to help Leap improving their website traffic and impression performance. With the result of both IMC and weighting rating method, the author proposed content marketing implementation plan for Search Engine Optimization (SEO), Social Media, and Email Marketing.

KEYWORDS: Content Marketing, Digital Marketing, Email Marketing, SEO, Social Media.

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the past few years, it gets easier for people to obtain information and technology. Nowadays, the existence of e-commerce is continuous in the industry (Hendarsyah, 2019). As one of the leading state-owned enterprises in Indonesia, Telkom Indonesia transformed its business from telecommunication company to digital telecommunication company. Actively innovating its digital products, Telkom creates an umbrella brand to handle all of these products with the name of Leap-Telkom Digital. This brand takes the role of handling 10 main Telkom's digital products, such as: Pijar Sekolah, BigBox, Netmonk, OCA, Antares, Toms, IndibizPAY, Logee, Agree, and PaDi UMKM. However, there are several problems faced by Leap-Telkom Digital in its brand awareness. This statement is proved by the result of the initial survey spread by the author. Based on the survey, only 18.8% people know about Leap, 15.6% might heard about Leap and the rest 65.6% has never heard about Leap before. In addition, from Leap's website performance, the user performance experienced decrease in its trendline with the equation $y = -3.1327x + 1043.5$. Meanwhile, the engagement rate is increasing with the equation $y = 0.0009x + 0.3116$. This shows that there's a contradiction in Leap's website performance. Besides, there's an uneven distribution of product knowledge in the internal Telkom itself. Based on the background problem stated, this research will be aimed to find out about the current performance of Leap's performance and propose an improved content marketing strategy in order to increase Leap's brand awareness, both to internal and external.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

II.1 Brand Building Blocks and CBBE Pyramid

The brand building blocks is a model developed by Kevin Lane Keller. This model was aimed to build a strong concept of a brand (Keller, 2001). CBBE model, in a form of CBBE pyramid, is used to determine the company's identity, meaning, response, and relationships.

II.2 Digital Marketing Funnel in B2B Business

There are four keys of digital marketing methods that commonly used in B2B business, namely: Search Engine Advertising, Content Marketing, Social Media, and Email Marketing (Hien & Nhu, 2022). However, according to Hien & Nhu, the strategy that has a

direct impact on customer’s purchase intention is Content Marketing. This research is also linear with the findings from Oscar and Louis (2021), as well as Wahid and Ahmed (2011).

II.3 Key Performance Indicators in Digital Marketing

There are two types of indicators in digital marketing: qualitative and quantitative (Saura & Palos-Sánchez, 2017). In qualitative methods, the KPI measured are: (1) Conversion; (2) Conversion Rate; (3) User. Meanwhile, the KPIs used in the quantitative methods are: (1) Impressions; (2) Traffic; (3) Unique Users; (4) Lead; (5) Conversion.

II.4 Gap Analysis

The method of gap analysis is used to detecting gaps of the market, product, or service quality. The measured gap is to determine the distinction between the desired market position and the current market position (Kim, 2018).

II.5 Integrated Marketing Communication

Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) is used to build customer engagement as well as increasing the firm’s value (Mihaela, 2015). There are seven steps in developing an effective IMC strategy: (1) Identify target audience; (2) Determine objectives; (3) Design communications; (4) Select channels; (5) Establish budget; (6) Decide on media mix; (7) Measure results; (8) Manage integrated marketing communications.

II.6 Conceptual Framework

The author developed the conceptual framework based on the findings of Gap Analysis that is conducted by interviewing the employees of Leap-Telkom Digital. The author’s analysis resulting in the conceptual framework as follows:

Figure 2. 1 Conceptual Framework

In conclusion, the research will focus on how to find an effective implementation of content marketing strategy using Social Media, SEO, and Email Marketing to increase the brand awareness of Leap-Telkom Digital.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

III.1 Research Design

The methodology that the author used in order to create an improved content marketing strategy for Leap-Telkom Digital is as follows:

Figure 3. 1 Research Design

The steps will begin by analyzing the business issue, and then create a gap analysis according to the issue findings. And then, once the conceptual framework is already proposed, the author will begin the research by developing questionnaire based on IMC theory. The author will do the testing for the questionnaire in order to spread it to the respondents. After the questionnaire is already collected, the author will analyze the result and then propose the content marketing strategy improvement for Leap-Telkom Digital.

III.2 Data Collection Methods

The research data will be collected using questionnaire development based on IMC theory. In IMC, the step of “Design the Communications” consists of four solutions: (1) Message strategy; (2) Creative strategy; (3) Message source; (4) Endorsements. Therefore, the questionnaire design would be as follows:

Table 3. 1 Questionnaire Design

Objective		Determine the effective communication type	Reference
Goal	Variables	Questions	
Determining preferred communication type	Message Strategy	Q1: I prefer to see Leap content related to the performance and quality of Telkom’s digital products	Kotler & Keller (2012)
		Q2: I prefer to see Leap content related to user experience when using Telkom’s digital products	
	Creative Strategy	Q3: I prefer to see Leap content related to information about attributes or benefits of Telkom’s digital products	
		Q4: I prefer to see Leap content that explains how Telkom’s digital products can help with my work	
	Message Source	Q5: I prefer to see Leap content promoted by relevant celebrities or artists	
		Q6: I prefer to see Leap content promoted by digital expert	
		Q7: I prefer to see Leap content promoted by reputable institutions or companies	
	Endorsements	Q8: I prefer to see Leap content that uses endorsement services	
Determining the importance of each communication type	Message Strategy	Q9: In my opinion, it is important for Leap to show content that explains Telkom’s digital products performance and quality	
		Q10: In my opinion, it is important for Leap to show content about user experiences who have used Telkom’s digital products	
	Creative Strategy	Q11: In my opinion, it is important for Leap to show content that contains information about the features or benefits of using Telkom’s digital products	
		Q12: When looking at Leap content, it is important for me to know how Telkom’s digital products can help my work	
	Message Source	Q13: In my opinion, Leap needs to use relevant celebrities or artists in promoting Telkom’s digital products	
		Q14: In my opinion, Leap needs to use digital experts in promoting Telkom’s digital products	
		Q15: In my opinion, it is important for Leap to show institutions or companies that have used or are currently using Telkom’s digital products	
	Endorsements	Q16: In my opinion, the use of endorsements is important for Leap to promote Telkom’s digital products	

III.4 Sampling Method

Since the population selected for this research is not random, which is the potential customers of Leap-Telkom Digital, the sampling used is the purposive non-probability sampling with the minimum respondents of more than 200 people.

III.5 Validity and Reliability Test

The questionnaire that is already developed and designed should be tested first before its spread to the respondents. The validity and reliability test will use SPSS with person’s correlation analysis and cronbach’s alpha.

III.6 Data Analysis Methods

The method that is used for analyzing the data is Weighted Scoring matrix to evaluate the qualitative into quantitative data (Odu, 2019). Therefore, the strategy development is based on a more accurate decision making process.

IV. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

IV.1 Weighting and Rating Result

The writer spread the questionnaire to 294 people within the target market, and it results to the calculation of weighting and rating as follows:

Table 4. 1 Weighting and Rating Matrix

Contents	Importance Level (Weight)	Average Weight	Weight	Preference Level (Rating)	Average Rating	Weighted Scores		Rank (Priority)
Performance and quality	Q1	4.16	0.13	Q9	4.42	44.22	5.58	5
User experience	Q2	4.20	0.13	Q10	4.40	44.01	5.60	4
Benefits information	Q3	4.26	0.13	Q11	4.45	44.49	5.73	2
How the product can help with work	Q4	4.43	0.13	Q12	4.48	44.76	6.01	1
Promoted by celebs or artists	Q5	3.78	0.11	Q13	3.87	38.67	4.42	7
Promotion by digital experts	Q6	4.31	0.13	Q14	4.34	43.40	5.67	3
Promotion by reputable institutions	Q7	4.23	0.13	Q15	4.35	43.47	5.57	6
Use of endorsements	Q8	3.65	0.11	Q16	3.95	39.52	4.36	8
		33.02	1					

According to the result above, the rank of content communication type is: (1) How the product can help with work; (2) Benefits information; (3) Promotion by digital experts; (4) User experience; (5) Performance and quality; (6) Promotion by reputable institutions; (7) Promoted by celebrities or artists; (8) Use of endorsements. To conclude the overall result of the analysis, here is the table that describe the rank of the content in order:

Table 4. 2 Content Rank

Rank	Content	Communication Type	Weighted Scores
1	Contents related to how Telkom’s digital product can help the customers with their work	Creative Strategy	6.01
2	Contents related to Telkom’s digital product attributes or benefits information	Creative Strategy	5.73
3	Contents that are promoted by digital experts	Message Source	5.67
4	Contents related to the user experience in using Telkom’s digital products	Message Strategy	5.60
5	Contents related to the information of Telkom’s digital product performance and quality	Message Strategy	5.58
6	Contents that are promoted by reputable and/or trusted institutions	Message Source	5.57
7	Contents that are promoted by relevant celebrities or artists	Message Source	4.42
8	Contents that are promoted by the use of endorsements	Endorsements	4.36

IV.2 Business Solution

According to the result analysis above, the content strategy that should be implemented by Leap-Telkom Digital are:

1. Prioritize the implementation of creative strategy
2. Choose the most suitable source for promotional purpose
3. Implement the right message strategy to the audience

IV.3 Implementation Plan

The result of data analysis is only for determining the communication type in “Designing the Communication” step of IMC. According to the research design, the next step is to select the channels where this content strategy will be put. Since Leap-Telkom Digital is currently implementing the SEO, Social Media, and Email Marketing, the channels that is used are also those three.

The main goal of making this strategy for an enhanced Content Marketing approach is to raise Leap-Telkom Digital brand awareness. As a result, Leap should promote material that will entice the viewers to visit the website. The goal is to improve Leap's website traffic and impressions, resulting in more leads and conversions, as well as increased brand recognition. As a result, below is the comprehensive execution plan for the Content Marketing strategy to improve Leap-Telkom Digital brand awareness: Since this research is based on the theory of Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) by Kotler & Keller (2012), there are two stages of implementation plan to conduct, which are:

1. Design the Communications

This stage is conducted based on the findings in IV.1 and IV.2, where the communication type is defined from Leap’s potential customers preference of contents. According to the business solution, these are the strategy that Leap-Telkom Digital should implement:

- a. Prioritize the implementation of creative strategy
- b. Choose the most suitable source for promotional purposes
- c. Implement the right message strategy to the audience

However, it is important to note that all content strategy that is formulated are as important. However, there should be a prioritization in implementing the strategy.

2. Selection of Channels

In order to determine what kind of channels that should be used, the author made an analysis based on funnels used in Leap-Telkom Digital. There are three main Content Marketing strategy used: SEO, Social Media, and Email Marketing. According to Kotler & Keller (2012), communication channels are divided into two categories: personal and non-personal (mass) communications. SEO and Social Media are used for non-personal communications, meanwhile, Email Marketing is used for personal communications.

For SEO strategy, the channels are categorized based on leap.digitalbisa.id website page. Contents on Leap’s website consists of: (1) About Us; (2) Product Catalogue; (3) Updated Articles. For Social Media strategy, the channels are categorized based on most-used Social Media for businesses. Email marketing would be for external and internal blast. To conclude the overall conclusion, the implementation plan is described like the table as follows:

Table 4. 3 Implementation Plan

Channel	Actions	People	Priority/Non-Priority	Updates Frequency	Place
SEO	Updating website’s information based on the content marketing planning	SEO Specialist	Priority	Once per three months (or updates based on evaluation result)	DMM Office
	Updating articles with firm keywords set based on the content marketing planning	SEO Specialist	Priority	Once per week	
	Conduct regular evaluation on website performance and make updates based on it	SEO Specialist	Non-Priority	Once per month	
Social Media	Updating social media contents based on content marketing planning	Social Media Specialist	Priority based on Channels Used	Everyday per week	
	Conduct regular evaluation on all social media performance and make updates based on it	Social Media Specialist	Non-Priority	Once per month	
Email Marketing	Updating email to blast to both internal and external	Email Admin, DMM Members	Priority	Should be conducted as soon as possible	
	Updating email contents based on content marketing planning	Email Admin	Priority	At least three days per week	

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis result, it can be concluded that Leap should improve its content marketing strategy through each funnel that they use. Overall, Leap uses three different channels in its content marketing: SEO, Social Media, and Email Marketing. All these channels should implement the improved content marketing strategy according to the writer’s analysis result in order to increase its brand awareness. Based on the analysis using weighting and rating calculation, the implementation plan for Leap as follows:

1. Implementation Plan for SEO Specialist

- a. Updating website’s information based on the content marketing planning
- b. Updating articles with firm keywords set based on the content marketing planning
- c. Conduct regular evaluation on website performance and make updates based on the evaluation

2. Implementation Plan for Social Media Specialist
 - a. Updating social media contents based on content marketing planning
 - b. Conduct regular evaluation on all social media performance and make updates based on it
3. Implementation Plan for Email Marketing Admin
 - a. Updating email to blast to both internal and external
 - b. Updating email contents based on content marketing planning

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Cite this Article: Vietra Shauma Ranabilla (2024). Proposed Content Marketing Strategy Improvement of Leap-Telkom Digital to Increase Brand Awareness. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 7(6), 4038-4045